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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 2

Pages: 199-203

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2552

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13996100

Manuscript Accepted: 10-01-2024

Innovative Curriculum Design, Classroom Management Strategies, Competencies, and Mathematics Teachers' Performance: A Causal Model

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Abstract

This study developed a causal model of innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies on elementary mathematics teachers' performance. A sample of 337 elementary school mathematics teachers from the nine elementary school districts within Cagayan de Oro City participated in the study. The research instrument employed in this study was a comprehensive questionnaire comprising eighty-three (83) items. Descriptive correlational and causal-comparative research designs were used in the study. Moreover, descriptive statistics were used to describe the parameters of the study. Inferential statistics such as Pearson product-moment correlation, multiple regression, and path analysis were used to answer inferential questions. Innovative curriculum design, particularly real-world application, and problem-solving skills were found to promote student engagement and effective teaching. A significant relationship exists between teachers' performance and innovative curriculum design, classroom management, and competencies. This indicates that the more innovative the curriculum design, the better classroom management strategies, and the more competent the mathematics teachers, the better the teachers' performance. Classroom management strategies, competencies, professional development, and differentiated instruction are the best predictors of teachers' performance. Causal model 3 is the best-fit model for teachers' performance anchored on educational policies and practices, innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and continuous professional development for elementary school mathematics teachers. This causal model is called "MeID's Model on Elementary School Teachers' Performance" which should be used by the teachers.

Keywords: *innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, teacher competencies, mathematics teachers' performance*

Introduction

Students in the Philippines often struggle with mathematics, as evidenced by their performance in international assessments. The 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, released by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), placed the Philippines 76th out of 81 countries in reading comprehension, mathematics, and science (Philippine Star, 2023). This poor performance highlights systemic issues within the Philippine education sector, including lack of resources, overcrowded classrooms, and an overloaded curriculum, which are further exacerbated by the government's neglect. The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS, 2019) also reported that the Philippines ranked last out of 58 countries in mathematics and science, emphasizing the urgent need for innovative curriculum design to improve elementary mathematics education. The Department of Education has responded with new curriculum designs under the K to 12 system, integrating contextualized and localized teaching materials, technology, and a spiral progression approach to reinforce students' understanding of mathematical concepts (Manila Bulletin, 2019).

Despite these curriculum innovations, several challenges remain, including the shortage of qualified and competent teachers who can effectively teach math and support students' success. The quality of education largely depends on the effectiveness of teachers, as they play a critical role in student learning outcomes (Utami, 2003; Sudjana, 2002, as cited by Ramatullah, 2016). This study investigates the impact of innovative curriculum design, effective classroom management strategies, and the development of specific competencies on mathematics teachers' performance. By employing a causal model, the research aims to identify the relationships between these factors and contribute to a framework that enhances mathematics education in the Philippines.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to develop a causal model to explore the effects of innovative curriculum designs, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies on mathematics teachers' performance in elementary schools. Specifically, the study sought to: (1) assess the level of innovative curriculum design in terms of: (a) real-world application and problem-solving; (b) technology integration; (c) inquiry-based learning; and (d) project-based learning and collaboration; (2) evaluate the level of classroom management strategies focusing on: (a) learning environment; (b) learning engagement; and (c) instructional methods; (3) measure the level of teacher competencies in terms of: (a) content knowledge and pedagogy; (b) differentiated instruction; (c) assessment and feedback; and (d) professional development; (4) determine the performance level of elementary school mathematics teachers in the division of Cagayan de Oro City; (5) analyze the significant relationships between teachers' performance and: (a) innovative curriculum designs; (b) classroom management strategies; and (c) teacher competencies; (6) identify which variables, either individually or in combination, most significantly influence the performance of mathematics teachers; and (7) evaluate which causal model best represents the factors affecting the performance of elementary school mathematics teachers.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a combination of descriptive-correlational, causal-comparative, and structural equation modeling (SEM) designs to explore the relationships between innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies on elementary mathematics teachers' performance. The descriptive-correlational design is utilized to describe and analyze the natural relationships among variables, while the causal-comparative design investigates differences between groups based on preexisting variables. These approaches help identify patterns and causal links within the selected variables. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to assess both direct and indirect relationships among the variables. SEM is an advanced analytical technique that uncovers causal connections between observed and latent variables, providing insights into how well the model explains variance and covariance patterns in the data. By integrating these methods, the study aims to develop a comprehensive causal model that enhances understanding of how innovative curriculum design, classroom management, and teacher competencies impact mathematics teachers' performance.

Respondents

The study focused on 337 elementary school mathematics teachers from the nine districts of Cagayan de Oro City. Participants were selected based on their specialization in mathematics and a minimum of three years of teaching experience, with no restrictions regarding age, gender, or ethnicity. The sampling procedure involved randomly selecting schools from each district and then contacting eligible mathematics teachers. After ensuring that participants met the criteria and obtained informed consent, a final cohort of 337 teachers was confirmed.

To achieve a representative sample, the study employed proportionate stratified sampling. The Raosoft Sample Size Calculator was used to determine the appropriate sample size, accounting for a 5% margin of error, a 95% confidence level, and a 50% response distribution. This approach ensured that the sample was statistically sound and representative of the population. Raosoft, developed by ProjectChampionz (2018), provided accurate and efficient sample size calculations, streamlining the process and reducing manual calculation errors.

Instrument

The research utilized a comprehensive questionnaire consisting of eighty-three items to evaluate various aspects of elementary school mathematics teachers' practices and competencies. The questionnaire was divided into four main sections. The first section focused on Innovative Curriculum Design, assessing teachers' practices related to real-world application, problem-solving, technology integration, inquiry-based learning, and project-based learning. These items were specifically developed to align with the study's objectives. The second section evaluated Classroom Management Strategies, encompassing aspects such as the learning environment, student engagement, and instructional methods. Items in this section were adapted from the Liceo de Cagayan University Teachers Assessment on Performance Standards to ensure they met recognized teaching standards.

The third section examined teacher competencies, including content knowledge, pedagogy, differentiated instruction, assessment and feedback, and professional development. Items were adapted from Malimit (2022) and the Research Performance Management System (RPMS) tool, widely used in the Philippines for evaluating teacher competencies. The fourth section focused on Teacher Performance, utilizing questionnaires from Acdal (2022) to capture various facets of teaching effectiveness within the study's context.

To ensure the clarity and relevance of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted with 30 teachers. Feedback from this test led to refinements, enhancing the instrument's validity and reliability. The final version was then administered to 337 teachers across public schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City. This comprehensive instrument aimed to thoroughly assess teaching practices, management strategies, and competencies, with the goal of improving teaching effectiveness and student outcomes in elementary mathematics.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study followed strict ethical guidelines. Initially, the researcher sought approval from the Office of the Dean of the School of Teacher Education. After receiving preliminary approval, the research proposal was reviewed by the Office of the Director of the Research Ethics Board to ensure compliance with ethical standards. Following this, a formal request was submitted to the Office of the Vice President for Research, Extension, Planning, and Innovation to conduct the study outside Liceo de Cagayan University.

Once all necessary approvals were secured, permission was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent to administer the survey questionnaire to the selected teachers. The researcher delivered a formal letter to the Schools Division Superintendent outlining the study's objectives and schedule. After gaining approval, a meeting with the teacher participants was organized.

During this meeting, participants received informed consent forms and the survey questionnaires. They were briefed on the study's procedures and assured that their responses would be confidential. Participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time without consequences. Those who agreed to participate completed the survey questionnaires, which were then collected by the

researcher for tabulation and analysis. The entire process was conducted with a focus on maintaining confidentiality and ensuring the validity of the data collected.

Data Analysis

To analyze and interpret the collected data, various statistical tools were employed. For addressing objectives 1-3 and assess the level of innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, teacher competencies, and the performance of elementary school mathematics teachers descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to describe the parameters of the study.

For problem 5, which examined the relationship between teachers' performance and the specified variables, Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized. This method assessed the strength and direction of the associations between teachers' performance and variables such as innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies.

In addressing problem 6, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine which variables, either independently or in combination, most significantly impacted teachers' performance. This technique facilitated the development of a predictive model to examine the causal relationships among the variables.

For problem 7, Path Analysis within the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) framework was used to identify the best-fit causal model explaining teachers' performance. This approach explored the complex relationships and causal connections among innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, teacher competencies, and other relevant factors, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teachers' performance.

Results and Discussion

This study developed a structural model on the factors influencing Elementary School Mathematics Teachers' performance, focusing on innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies. The results revealed a strong emphasis on real-world application and problem-solving skills within the curriculum, as evidenced by the highest mean score ($M=4.58$, $SD=0.52$). Collaborative learning, particularly through project-based activities, was also highly prioritized ($M=4.55$, $SD=0.638$). Technology integration was satisfactory ($M=3.69$, $SD=0.87$), while inquiry-based learning received moderate attention ($M=3.61$, $SD=1.00$). Overall, the perception of innovative curriculum design was positive, with an overall mean score of $M=4.11$ ($SD=0.76$).

In terms of classroom management strategies, teachers exhibited very high levels of effectiveness, especially in creating conducive learning environments and employing effective instructional strategies, both scoring $M=4.76$ ($SD=0.45$ and 0.79 , respectively). Learning engagement, though slightly lower, still scored highly ($M=4.71$, $SD=0.46$), resulting in an overall mean score of $M=4.74$ ($SD=0.57$), indicating a very high level of classroom management.

Teacher competencies were also rated very highly, particularly in professional development and differentiated instruction, both receiving a mean score of $M=4.76$ ($SD=0.57$ and 0.79 , respectively). Content knowledge and pedagogy were also strong ($M=4.71$, $SD=0.46$), leading to an overall mean score of $M=4.74$ ($SD=0.57$), reflecting a high level of teacher competency.

The performance of teachers was found to be outstanding, especially in areas of professional engagement ($M=4.64$, $SD=0.49$), personal growth ($M=4.63$, $SD=0.50$), and content knowledge ($M=4.58$, $SD=0.53$). The overall mean score of $M=4.60$ ($SD=0.51$) indicated an outstanding level of performance.

The study also identified strong positive relationships between teachers' performance and variables such as classroom management, differentiated instruction, and professional development ($p<.05$). Moderate positive relationships were observed with real-world application, project-based learning, and pedagogy ($p<.05$). However, technology integration and inquiry-based learning showed weaker relationships with performance ($p<.05$).

Among the factors influencing teachers' performance, project-based learning, professional development, and teacher competencies were particularly significant. Professional development and teacher competencies had a more substantial impact on performance compared to project-based learning.

Causal Model 3 was determined to be the best-fit model for explaining Elementary School Mathematics Teachers' performance. It met the criteria for an acceptable model fit across seven standard indices, demonstrating strong reliability and validity. In conclusion, this study highlights the critical role of professional development, teacher competencies, and innovative curriculum design in enhancing teachers' performance in mathematics education, offering valuable insights for educators and policymakers aiming to improve educational outcomes.

Conclusions

Elementary Math Teachers have a very high level of innovative curriculum design, especially in real-world application and problem-solving. High level of technology integration, inquiry-based and project-based learning, and collaboration. They are highly effective in creating engaging learning environments, delivering instructional content, and managing classrooms.

The teachers have high level of competencies in knowledge and pedagogy, and very high level of competencies in differentiated

instruction, assessment and feedback, and professional development. As well as the overall teacher competencies. They also perform very high across all six components of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST).

A significant relationship exists between their performance and levels of innovative curriculum design, classroom management strategies, and teacher competencies. professional development is the most significant predictor of performance, followed by teacher competencies and project-based learning and collaboration.

Structural Model 3, also known as MeID's Model, affirms that Elementary Math Teachers' performance is positively influenced by elementary teachers' classroom management and strategies, problem-based expertise in innovative curriculum design, project-based learning and collaboration, and professional development. Assessment and feedback, differentiated instruction, and content knowledge and pedagogy also significantly impact teaching competencies.

The following recommendations are designed as a direct response to the research findings and conclusions discussed previously. These suggestions are intended to provide guidance and support to the Department of Education, school administrations, educators, and fellow researchers in developing comprehensive programs that specifically address teaching competencies and their evident impact on student learning outcomes.

Department of Education. The Department of Education may consider integrating innovative curriculum designs that emphasize real-world application and problem-solving skills into the existing curriculum frameworks. Providing professional development opportunities focused on technology integration and inquiry-based learning is encouraged to enhance teachers' competencies and improve overall classroom management strategies.

School Heads. School heads are encouraged to prioritize creating a conducive learning environment that fosters active student engagement. This includes promoting project-based learning and facilitating collaboration among teachers. Additionally, school heads could implement regular assessments and feedback mechanisms focused on students to monitor and enhance the learning experience effectively. These measures could ensure that students receive continuous, constructive feedback and support tailored to their needs, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes.

Teachers. Teachers are encouraged to actively engage in continuous professional development programs to strengthen their content knowledge, pedagogy, and differentiated instruction skills. Emphasizing real-world application and problem-solving in their teaching practices is suggested to enhance students' critical thinking and practical skill development.

Future Researchers. Future research may explore more in-depth studies on targeted professional development programs or curriculum enhancements and their impact on teachers' performance and student outcomes. Investigating other factors contributing to teaching performance is also suggested for a more comprehensive understanding and improvement of educational practices.

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